

Appendix 1

The Neighbour Net dendrogram for 216 *Tulipa suaveolens* specimens

Appendix 2

Scatter plot obtained from principal component analysis of 216 specimens of *T. suaveolens* derived from 250 polymorphic ISSR loci

Appendix 3

Mean likelihood $L(K)$ and variance per K values generated by STRUCTURE on dataset containing 216 specimens across 250 polymorphic ISSR bands. **a.** Delta K values of STRUCTURE **b** and **c.** Plots for detecting the number of K groups that best fit the data. **d.** Plot of mean likelihood $L(K)$ and variance per K value

